

Mobility Plans for Universities: A Bibliometric Analysis

*Mobility Plans for Universities:
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*Planes de Movilidad para Universidades:
Un Análisis Bibliométrico*

Edson Company Colalto Junior¹

edson.colalto@cpspos.sp.gov.br

Lucas Santos de Queiroz¹

lucas.queiroz@cpspos.sp.gov.br

Celio Daroncho³

c179401@dac.unicamp.br

John Roberto Maiellaro²

João.maiellaro@fatec.sp.gov.br

Alexandre Formigoni¹

Alexandre.formigoni@cpspos.sp.gov.br

1 – Programa de Mestrado Profissional do CEETEPS

2 – Faculdade de Tecnologia da Zona Leste

3 – Universidade Estadual de Campinas

Abstract: Urban mobility in universities is increasingly prominent due to its influence on the academic environment and the quality of life of students, faculty, and staff. This article aims to identify the scientific production related to university mobility plans from 2018 to 2022. To achieve this goal, the following specific objectives were established: to identify the principal authors involved in this field of study, to identify the leading institutions of affiliation of these authors, to analyze the collaboration networks between researchers, and to evaluate the impact of publications related to mobility plans for universities. The analysis of the results of this research provides a comprehensive view of the topic, allowing us to precisely analyze and evaluate the principal authors, affiliation institutions, the impact factor of the authors and publications, and the collaboration networks between researchers. This bibliometric analysis allows us to conclude that the topic of mobility plans for universities, despite returning a relatively low number of productions between 2018 and 2022, is a field of study that is expanding and of growing academic interest. Therefore, it is recommended that research be continued in this field to pro-

duce innovative and practical solutions to promote mobility in the academic environment.

Keywords: *Mobility plans; Universities; Bibliometrics.*

Resumo: A mobilidade urbana nas universidades é um tópico em crescente destaque devido à sua influência no ambiente acadêmico e na qualidade de vida dos estudantes, professores e funcionários. Este artigo tem como objetivo geral identificar a produção científica relacionada a planos de mobilidade para universidades, no período de 2018 a 2022. Para alcançar esse objetivo, têm-se como objetivos específicos: identificar os principais autores envolvidos nesse campo de estudo; identificar as principais instituições de afiliação desses autores; analisar as redes de colaboração entre pesquisadores, e; avaliar o impacto das publicações relacionadas a planos de mobilidade para universidades. A análise dos resultados desta pesquisa

Recebido
Received
Recibido
01 mai. 2024

Aceito
Accepted
Aceptado
28 ago. 2024

Publicado
Published
Publicado
27 set. 2024

<https://git.fateczl.edu.br>

e_ISSN
2965-3339

DOI
10.29327/2384439.2.4-5

São Paulo
v. 2 | n. 4
v. 2 | i. 4
e24222
Setembro
Septembre
Septiembre
2024

fornece uma visão abrangente a respeito da temática, permitindo analisar e avaliar precisamente os principais autores, instituições de afiliação, fator de impacto dos autores e das publicações e as redes de colaboração entre os pesquisadores. Esta análise bibliométrica permite concluir que a temática dos planos de mobilidade para universidades, apesar de retornar um número relativamente baixo de produções no período entre 2018 e 2022, é um campo de estudo em expansão e de crescente interesse acadêmico. Portanto, recomenda-se a continuidade de pesquisas nesse campo, visando a produção de soluções inovadoras e eficazes para a promoção da mobilidade no ambiente acadêmico.

Palavras-chave: Planos de mobilidade; Universidades; Bibliometria.

Resumen: La movilidad urbana en las universidades es un tema cada vez más destacado debido a su influencia en el entorno académico y la calidad de vida de estudiantes, profesores y personal. Este artículo tiene como objetivo general identificar la producción científica relacionada con los planes de movilidad para las universidades, de 2018 a 2022. Para lograr este objetivo, los siguientes objetivos específicos son: identificar a los principales autores involucrados en este campo de estudio; identificar las principales instituciones de filiación de estos autores; analizar redes de colaboración entre investigadores, y; evaluar el impacto de las publicaciones relacionadas con los planes de movilidad para las universidades. El análisis de los resultados de esta investigación proporciona una visión integral del tema, permitiéndonos analizar y evaluar con precisión a los principales autores, instituciones de filiación, factor de impacto de los autores y publicaciones y redes de colaboración entre investigadores. Este análisis bibliométrico permite concluir que el tema de los planes de movilidad universitaria, a pesar de arrojar un número de producciones relativamente bajo en el período comprendido entre 2018 y 2022, es un campo de estudio en expansión y de creciente interés académico. Por lo tanto, se recomienda continuar la investigación en este campo, con el objetivo de producir soluciones innovadoras y efectivas para promover la movilidad en el entorno académico.

Palabras clave: Planes de movilidad; Universidades; Bibliometría.

1 INTRODUCTION

Urban mobility is relevant in urban planning and city management agendas (ORTUZAR, 2011). In the academic context, scientific production on mobility has expanded considerably, covering various topics and areas of study. However, a specific aspect of this field has gained prominence: mobility within universities. With the growth of higher education institutions and the diversification of their campuses (BRASIL, 2015), mobility issues within and around universities have become crucial to ensuring an environment conducive to learning and research (CASQUEIRO; IRFFI; SILVA, 2020).

The general objective of this study is to identify the scientific production related to mobility plans for universities from 2018 to 2022. To achieve this goal, the following specific objectives are set: to identify the principal authors involved in this field of study, to identify their main institutions of affiliation, to analyze the collaboration networks between researchers, and to evaluate the impact of publications related to mobility plans for universities.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Urban Mobility

Urban mobility is the term used to describe the movement of people and goods within urban areas, regardless of the means of transport used. This includes both public and individual transport, whether motorized or not (PERO; STEFANELLI, 2015).

According to Segunda Costa (2008), mobility encompasses interactions between spaces inhabited by permanent residents, the means and objects used for transportation, and relationships with other individuals that make up society. On the other hand, urban mobility defines all movements within a city. For mobility to be efficient, transportation services must be offered appropriately. One of these transportation services is provided by urban public transportation, which plays a crucial role in any city, and its management must be carefully planned to ensure financial profitability and inclusion and meet the community's needs, avoiding its focus solely on obtaining revenue. Such contributions to this service must be interpreted as an investment, with controls and criteria as such (VASCONCELLOS; CARVALHO; PEREIRA, 2011).

As highlighted by Carvalho (2016), public managers have the responsibility to implement public policies that promote a fair, efficient, and effective mobility system based on a socially inclusive approach and supported by a financial structure that does not leave the less favored aside. In addition, these policies must be oriented toward reducing the negative externalities associated with urban mobility.

However, Scaringella (2001) states that several elements have a direct influence on the operations of these services, such as government inefficiency in fully covering the entire urban area and its respective population, serving both central

and peripheral regions, the considerable number of vehicles in circulation and the deteriorated state of transport routes.

Daroncho et al. (2023) address urban mobility and its evolution, highlighting the importance of transport systems to ensure adequate mobility in urban areas. They also explore the importance of sustainable mobility and list the impacts of Information Technologies on urban mobility. These items are of the utmost importance for mobility in urban areas, and it is necessary and imperative that they be the focus of mobility plans.

2.2 Mobility plan

As established by the City Statute (BRASIL, 2001), urban mobility plans are fundamental for implementing mobility policy in cities and are mandatory for municipalities with more than 500,000 inhabitants. However, with the enactment of Law No. 12,587/2012, this obligation began to follow the criteria of urban master plans, applying to municipalities with more than 20,000 inhabitants, resulting in a significant increase in the number of municipalities involved (BRASIL, 2012).

However, the resources available, mainly through parliamentary amendments, did not encourage smaller municipalities to develop their mobility plans and, often facing institutional weaknesses, such as the lack of specific legislation, only 36% of the municipalities served complied with the obligation (IPEA, 2012). One of the problems identified by Lima Neto and Galindo (2015) is the lack of precise legal instruments for the institutionalization of urban mobility plans, in addition to the fact that, on average, municipalities with institutionalized plans received fewer resources per capita than those municipalities that did not develop their mobility plans, indicating the need for adjustments in the financing criteria.

3 METHOD

This study was carried out through bibliometric research, which, according to Pritchard (1969), refers to using statistical and mathematical procedures to quantitatively analyze bibliographic production. Bibliometric analysis is applied in studies from different areas. For example, Pohlmann, Formigoni, and Stettiner (2020) conducted a bibliometric analysis to survey the number of studies that address the theme of augmented reality in the industry.

This work considered articles published between 2018 and 2022 in the Scopus and Science Direct databases. These two databases are justified because they are broad databases that index studies from different areas, serve all countries, and have clear and easy-to-use advanced search fields.

When accessing the Scopus database page, it was defined that the search type would be for articles, the keywords would be " *mobility plan* " and " *university*," and the advanced search field would be "Title, abstract, and keywords." With the keywords, the string " *mobility plan **" AND " *universit **" was established, where the asterisk, a wildcard character, indicates that it can also return words derived

from *the plan*, such as *plans* or *planning*, and *university*, such as *universities*. For the given period, 19 articles were found in the Scopus database.

When accessing the Science Direct database page, the same type of search, keywords, and advanced search field were used as in Scopus. However, the *string* used was ("*mobility plan*" OR "*mobility planning*") AND ("*university*" OR "*universities*") because on this database page, the asterisk character is not accepted as a wildcard character in a search *string*. Four articles were found in the Science Direct database for the determined search period.

Table 1 depicts searching for information about articles in the two databases selected for the research.

Table 1 - Search for articles in Scopus and Science Direct databases

SEARCHING ARTICLES IN DATABASES	
Database	<i>Scopus and Science Direct</i>
Search type	Articles
Search field	Title, Abstract, and Keywords
<i>Scopus</i> database	19
<i>Science Direct</i> database	4

Source: the authors.

To extract data on annual scientific production, authors, most relevant sources and affiliations, most cited articles and authors, scientific production by country, collaboration network between authors, and correlation between abstract terms, we used the statistical software R (version 4.3.1) with the *Bibliometrix package*, which provides tools for analyzing the scientific mapping workflow. With this package, it was possible to generate graphs, tables, correlation, and co-citation maps.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The R software with the *Bibliometrix package* made it possible to unify the files exported from the databases and exclude duplicate articles, that is, articles with the same title and authors found in both databases. Four duplicate articles were excluded, and 19 were considered for the bibliometric analysis.

Figure 1 and Table 1 depict the annual scientific production found. Based on the keywords used for the search, the year with the most significant scientific production regarding the topic addressed in this work was 2022, with 6 publications found, and the year with the smallest number of publications was 2018, with only 1.

Figure 1 - Annual Scientific Production on Urban Mobility Plans
Annual Scientific Production

Source: the authors (with data obtained from *Bibliometrix*)

Table 1 - Annual scientific production figures between 2018 and 2022

Year	Number of articles
2018	1
2019	5
2020	2
2021	5
2022	6

Source: the authors (with data obtained from *Bibliometrix*)

The ten most relevant sources are shown in Figure 2 and Table 2. It can be seen that *Transportation Research Procedia* has three articles published on the topic between 2018 and 2022, followed by *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, with 2. The others have 1 article each.

Figure 2 - Most relevant sources
Most Relevant Sources

Source: the authors (adapted from *Bibliometrix*)

Table 2 - Total articles by source

Sources	No. of articles
<i>Transportation Research Procedia</i>	3
<i>Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing</i>	2
<i>2021 2nd Sustainable Cities Latin America Conference, SCLA 2021</i>	1
<i>AIP Conference Proceedings</i>	1
<i>Case Studies on Transport Policy</i>	1
<i>Dyna (Spain)</i>	1
<i>European Transport Research Review</i>	1
<i>Frontiers in Sustainable Cities</i>	1
<i>Geotechnical Special Publication</i>	1
<i>Technological Information</i>	1

Source: the authors (adapted from *Bibliometrix*)

Extracting only the local impact factor with Bibliometrix, measured through the h-index, was possible. The source with the highest impact factor is *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, with an h-index of 2. From 2018 to 2022, this source had two articles with two or more citations. This data is evident in Table 3, which shows that this source obtained seven citations.

Table 3 - Local impact factor by source

Source	h-index	Quotes
<i>Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing</i>	2	7
<i>2021 2nd Sustainable Cities Latin America Conference, SCLA 2021</i>	1	2
<i>AIP Conference Proceedings</i>	1	9
<i>Dyna (Spain)</i>	1	1
<i>European Transport Research Review</i>	1	4
<i>Frontiers in Sustainable Cities</i>	1	1
<i>International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education</i>	1	4
<i>ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information</i>	1	14
<i>Proceedings of the 2019 IEEE 1st Sustainable Cities Latin America Conference, SCLA 2019</i>	1	1
<i>Proceedings Of the International Astronautical Congress, IAC</i>	1	1

Source: the authors (adapted from *Bibliometrix*)

Figure 3 and Table 4 show the most relevant authors. In Figure 3, the authors are classified according to the total number of publications and, in Table 4, by the impact factor. In both cases, the authors Papantoniou, Yannis, Attard, Ignaccolo, Inturri, and Vlahogianni stand out, having an h index of 2 and at least 2 published articles.

Table 4 - Local impact factor by author

Author	h-index	No. of citations
ATTARD M.	2	7
IGNACCOLO M.	2	23
INTURRI G.	2	23
PAPANTONIOUS P.	2	8
VLAHOIANANI E.	2	7
YANNIS G.	2	8
ALONSO F.	1	1
ANTONIALI F.	1	8
AVARMAA R.	1	1
BUTRON-REVILLA C.	1	3

Source: the authors (adapted from *Bibliometrix*)

Figure 3 - Most relevant authors

Source: the authors (adapted from *Bibliometrix*)

Table 5 shows the affiliations, that is, the institutions or universities with which the authors are affiliated. It can be seen that the institutions with the most affiliates are the *University of Catania*, which has five affiliates, followed by the *National Technical University of Athens*, with 3, and *Universidad de Sevilla*, *Universidad de San Agustín de Arequipa*, *University of Malta*, and *University of Monterrey*, with two affiliates each. The presence of two Brazilian universities stands out: the *University of Passo Fundo* and the *Federal University of Lavras*.

Table 5 - Most relevant affiliations

Affiliations	No. of articles
<i>University of Catania</i>	5
<i>National Technical University of Athens</i>	3
<i>University of Seville</i>	2
<i>National University of San Agustín de Arequipa</i>	2
<i>University of Malta</i>	2
<i>University of Monterrey</i>	2
<i>Interuniversity Center for Economic and Mobility Research</i>	1
<i>Radford University</i>	1
<i>National University of Colombia - Headquarters Bogotá</i>	1
<i>National University of Colombia - Manizales Headquarters</i>	1
<i>University of Passo Fundo</i>	1
<i>Federal University of Lavras</i>	1
<i>University College Dublin</i>	1
<i>University of Bologna</i>	1
<i>University of Tartu</i>	1
<i>University of Valencia</i>	1
<i>University of West Attica</i>	1
<i>University Research Institute on Traffic and Road Safety</i>	1

Source: the authors (adapted from *Bibliometrix*)

Regarding scientific production by country, Figure 4 and Table 6 show that Italy stands out with four publications, followed by Peru and Spain, with 2 each, and

Brazil, Colombia, France, Germany, Greece, Mexico, and the United States, with 1 publication each.

Figure 4 - Scientific production by country

Source: the authors (adapted from *Bibliometrix*)

Table 6 - Number of publications by country

Country	Publications
Italy	4
Peru	2
Spain	2
Brazil	1
Colombia	1
France	1
Germany	1
Greece	1
Mexico	1
United States	1

Source: the authors (adapted from *Bibliometrix*)

When analyzing the topic's relevance according to the number of citations each article obtained, Table 7 lists the articles that received 2 or more citations from 2018 to 2022, which can be considered the most relevant to this study's topic.

With *Bibliometrix*, it was possible to establish which keywords were most frequently found in the abstracts, as shown in Figure 5, and to draw a correlation map between them, as shown in Figure 6. This allows one to perceive the possible research approaches on the topic.

Figure 7 - Co-citation map between authors

Source: the authors (adapted from Bibliometrix)

After this general survey, considering what was found in the search in the "Title, abstract, keyword" field, an analysis of the titles of each article was carried out to verify the number of studies that relate mobility plans with universities. The result is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 - Analysis of article titles

Improving Sustainable Mobility in university campuses: The case study of Sapienza University
Collaborative soft mobility planning for university cities, the case of Pavia
Developing a sustainable mobility action plan for university campuses
A framework for improving sustainable mobility in Higher Education campuses: the case study of Gatar University
Large-scale mobility on the moon by transferring terrestrial autonomy capabilities
Development of a roadmap for the implementation of a sustainable mobility action plan in university campuses of emerging countries
Study to promote sustainable mobility in universities
Urban accessibility analysis from road interventions through geographic information systems case study the road network of the Quibdó Municipality in Colombia analysis of urban accessibility from road interventions through geographic information systems case study of the street mall of the municipality of Quibdó in Colombia
Discovering urban mobility patterns and demand for uses of urban spaces from mobile phone data
An analysis of students' urban mobility using the Arequipa smart mobility application
Investigating mobility gaps on university campuses
Introducing a mobility-on-demand system beyond COVID-19 evidence from users' perspective
Analysis of mobility patterns in selected university campus areas
Innovative school routing problem for the new normality
Linking public transport user satisfaction with service accessibility for sustainable mobility planning
Casual carpooling is a strategy to support the implementation of mobility as a service in a developing country
Natural Bridge Virginia complementary geotechnical investigation and analysis methods for mobility planning
Using getisord GI maps to understand bicycle mobility during the winter season in Valencia, Spain
The regional cycle network of Sardinia upgrading the accessibility of rural areas through a comprehensive island-wide cycle network

Source: the authors.

In Table 2, the titles highlighted in green are those related to mobility plans at a university, totaling 8 articles. The titles highlighted in blue relate mobility to students or schools, and the titles in orange are works that deal with mobility or mobility plans related to some other subject.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study carried out a bibliometric analysis of mobility plans for universities between 2018 and 2022. The research sought to achieve its general and specific objectives by mapping, understanding, and contextualizing the scientific production related to this field.

From the search in the Scopus and Science Direct databases, using the keywords “*mobility plan*” and “*university*,” it was possible to identify the principal authors involved in this field of study and analyze the collaboration networks between these researchers. It is noted that there is still no global collaboration network between the authors, but only local collaborations, that is, only collaborations between researchers from the same university or the same country, which can lead to the conclusion that it is a field of study that is still expanding.

The bibliometric analysis allowed the researchers' affiliation institutions to be identified precisely, revealing academic centers that have stood out in scientific production on university mobility plans.

Regarding the assessment of the impact of publications related to mobility plans for universities, this analysis of the impact factor and number of citations of the publications reveals the relevance and pertinence of the topic for the academic community.

Based on this bibliometric analysis, it is possible to conclude that the theme of mobility plans for universities, despite having a relatively low number of productions between 2018 and 2022, is an expanding field of study of growing academic interest. Therefore, it is recommended that research in this field be continued, aiming at producing innovative and effective solutions for promoting mobility in the academic environment.

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